

ENGAGEMENT FOUNDATIONS & BEST PRACTICES

Who? Audience: public health agencies, CBOs, nonprofits

Why? Meaningful involvement builds equity, resilience

Effective community engagement fosters trust, ensures inclusivity, and leads to sustainable, community-driven solutions. Equitable engagement requires listening, collaboration, and shared decision making.

How? Key principles of authentic engagement

Trust-Building

Engage early, consistently, and transparently to establish credibility.

Equity-Centered Outreach

Recognize and address systemic barriers to participation.

Cultural Humility

Value lived experiences and co-create solutions with the community.

Accessibility & Inclusion

Ensure materials and meetings are accessible (language, format, location).

What? Strategies for success:

Meet Communities Where They Are

Host events in familiar spaces such as churches, libraries, or community centers.

Use Asset-Based Approaches

Recognize and uplift existing community strengths rather than focusing solely on deficits.

Engage Beyond Surveys

Utilize focus groups, listening sessions, and participatory decision-making.

Use the playbook to further develop best practices and engagement strategies and examples.

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- **Chapter 5:** [Best Practices for Conducting Community Engaged Research](#)
- **Chapter 2:** [Strengthening Partnerships to Reach Communities](#)

ACTION STEPS

- Identify key stakeholders and trusted community leaders.
- Develop engagement activities that prioritize two-way communication.
- Use a trauma-informed approach to acknowledge past harms and build trust.